

European Public Local Authorities' Network for
driving the Energy Transition

D5.5 - EU Open Call

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March, 2022 (M7) - WP5, D5.5

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101032450. The views expressed in this publication are the sole responsibility of the author/s and do not necessarily reflect the views of the European Commission.

Technical References

Project Acronym	ePLANET
Project Title	EUROPEAN PUBLIC LOCAL AUTHORITIES' NETWORK FOR DRIVING THE ENERGY TRANSITION

Deliverable No.	D5.5
Dissemination Level	PU
Work Package	WP5 - REPLICATION AND NETWORKING
Lead beneficiary	04 (FEDARENE)
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	01 (CIMNE)
Due date of deliverable	31 March 2022
Actual submission date	15 April 2022

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Versions

Version	Date	Changes	Edited by
0.1	12/04/22	Full draft version	Matthias Watzak-Helmer
0.2	14/04/22	Reviewed version	Josep Mayos
1	15/04/22	Final version	Matthias Watzak-Helmer

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Executive Summary

ePLANET project is a Coordination and Support Action cofounded by the European Commission through Horizon 2020 program. ePLANET aims to deploy a new clustering governance for energy transition based on a digital framework to share harmonized information, facilitating the adoption of coordinated energy transition actions by the European public sector.

This document proves the availability of the open call on the EU survey platform and provides information on the launched open call for follower regions. It describes the aim of the open call as well as the target group and describes which regional actors shall join ePLANET project as followers. The application process is described and the application form for the ongoing phase 1 of the open call is shown.

There will be four deliverables describing the selection and activities with the follower regions. The deliverables “D5.5 EU Open Call” and “D5.6 Evaluation report with assessment criteria matrix” will be directly linked to the selection process. The deliverables “D5.7 Follower Regions Evaluation Questionnaire” and “D5.8 Reports on join exchange activities experiences” will refer to the activities with the selected regions.

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Abbreviations and acronyms

ABBREVIATION OR ACRONYM	DESCRIPTION
MoA	Memorandum of Adhesion

1 Open Call process

1.1 Aim of the open call

With the open call ePLANET wants to identify up to 6 follower regions to benefit from and contribute to the ePLANET platform and multi-level governance approach.

1.2 Target group

The open call focuses on:

- Regional and (cluster of) local public authorities
- Local and regional (Energy) Agencies
- Other Stakeholder (e.g., associations, initiatives, energy communities, ESCO, private companies) if they can proof the support from regional / local authorities

1.3 Application process and deadlines

The selection of the follower regions is done within several steps:

- Open call phase 1: Option to express interest to join as follower region - March-May 22
- Open call phase 2: Full application including data submission according to assessment matrix (details will be submitted within “D5.6 Evaluation report with assessment criteria matrix” until M12 /Aug 22) - June 22
- Evaluation of the applications - July 22
- Selection of the follower regions and matching with ePLANET regions - July 22
- Signature of MoA - Aug 22

2 EU Open Call on EUsurvey

The Open Call for interested regions was published on EU survey on the 30th of March and will stay opened until the second phase of the Open Call starts, which is foreseen for the 1st of June.

2.1 Application form

The Open Call from the EU survey platform is shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 and is online available at the moment the deliverable is submitted under the link: https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/ePLANET_twinningregion.

Save a backup on your local computer (disable if you are using a public/shared computer)

ePLANET open call for twinning regions

Fields marked with * are mandatory.

We are looking for motivated Authorities and Energy Agencies to join our obliging team as regional partner.

ePLANET aims to improve the coordination between local authorities and regional governments by fostering the digitalisation of energy data available in dispersed data sources.

The improvements in the multi-level governance and the developed energy data visualizations will be designed and implemented together with three regions:

- Crete Island (Greece)
- Girona Region (Spain)
- Zlín region (Czech Republic)

The project team and especially our regional partners are searching for regional alliances to work together on the Energy Transition. The ePLANET project offers future follower regions a wide variety of support including

- study visits to one of the project regions,
- peer to peer support and
- tailored webinars and workshops.

Further information about ePLANET and the open call can be found on the projects website www.eplaneth2020.eu as well as on <https://fedarene.org/>.

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Figure 1 - ePLANET open call 1/2

Expression of interest

* Name

* email

* Name of your organization

EU member states

* Region

How do you want to stay in contact with ePLANET (1)

- I want to receive the ePLANET newsletter
 I want to be invited to ePLANET events

(1) You can change your mind at any time by clicking the unsubscribe link in the footer of any email you receive from us, or by contacting us at info@eplaneth2020.eu. We will treat your information with respect. For more information about our privacy practices please visit our website (www.eplaneth2020.eu). By clicking below, you agree that we may process your information in accordance with these terms.

GDPR Permission

*

I accept your terms of conditions. I agree that ePLANET project partners will use the information provided on this form to contact and inform me about the opportunities to become a follower region. In case I selected the option I further agree to be contacted via newsletter and/or receive invitations to events. I know that I can withdraw my expression of interest anytime by contacting the ePLANET team at info@eplaneth2020.eu. The privacy policy of ePLANET can be read on the project website www.eplaneth2020.eu/privacy-policy/.

Submit

Figure 2 - ePLANET open call 2/2

